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“LOST SLIPPERS”

I lost my slippers one quiet day,
By the shore where we used to stay.
The wind was soft, the tide was low,
But still, they slipped and chose to go.

They were old, not new or bright,
But they held memories, soft and light—
Of walks with you on rainy ground,
And quiet talks without a sound.

Each step we took, they felt it too,
The laughter shared, the skies so blue.
Though torn and simple, they were mine,
Like love that blooms without a sign.

When they were gone, I stood alone,
Barefoot now, but not unknown.
For in the sand, I saw so clear—
Their prints beside yours, still near.

I lost my slippers, yes, it's true,
But not the love I shared with you.
For even when the soles are gone,
The heart remembers—it walks on.